

Consortium of European Research Libraries

Newsletter 1 May 2000

For contact details see: <http://www.cerl.org/>

New files on the HPB

Our most important news, as ever, is the new files becoming available on the HPB. We are happy to announce that with the recent addition of the Oxford records, the HPB file now contains c. 864,500 records.

Oxford

Oxford has an extremely rich, diverse and fragmented library service provided by over 100 independently managed library units. The file currently contains 44,560 records from Oxford libraries, including the Bodleian, Taylorian, Ashmolean, as well as College and Departmental libraries. These were extracted on the basis of record quality only and therefore represent only a small proportion of the total number of printed books of the hand press period in Oxford. Records in this file have been catalogued book in hand and to full Oxford Antiquarian standard.

It is possible to search in the author indexes on any names associated with the work. Names are entered not only for the main author of a work, but also for editors, translators, illustrators, engravers, printers and publishers (where these are known).

The Library of
Congress Name

L'Obel, Matthias de. *Plantarum seu stirpium icones.*
Antuerpiae, Ex officina Christophori Plantini, Architypographi
regij. M.D.LXXXI. (*Magdalen College - With donation
inscription, and hand coloured illustrations*)

Authority File is used to ensure that names are drawn together, however many variants are apparent on title pages and in colophons. Library of Congress subject headings are also included. Places of printing are included both in the form that appears on the title page or in the colophon, as well as in a standardised hierarchical place name.

There are several cataloguing initiatives currently in progress in Oxford and there will be updates to the file in the future. More information on the Oxford file may be found on <http://www.cerl.hpb/oxfdesc.htm>.

SB16

The next file to be added to the HPB is the SB16 file from the Kungliga Bibliotek in Stockholm – c. 6,000 records based on the bibliography of 17th-century Swedish material compiled by I. Collijn.

In progress

CERL is in the happy position that it has been offered a number of important files for inclusion in the HPB. The following files are scheduled to be loaded in the next two years:

- c. 4,500 records from the National Library of Russia, St Petersburg (followed by regular annual updates)

- c. 26,000 Short-Title records from the *Cathedral Libraries Catalogue, Books printed on the Continent of Europe before 1701 in the Libraries of the Anglican Cathedrals of England and Wales* (no updates)
- c. 47,000 records from the University of London Libraries, London
- c. 19,000 records from the Helsinki University Library, Helsinki
- c. 4,500 records from the National Library, Lisbon
- c. 1 million records from the Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek, Göttingen
- c. 35,000 records from the VD17 and VD16 (Supplement file), Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, München (The VD17 records will replace the 17th-century BSB material currently in the HPB and will be linked to digital images)
- more than 11,000 records from the National Library of Wales, Aberystwyth

Once this programme of file loads has been completed over 1,150,000 new records will have been added to the HPB, bringing the total number of records just over 2 million.

HPB Manual for Eureka on the Web

The HPB Manual for Eureka on the Web has been compiled by the Executive Manager, the Advisory Task Group, and representatives from RLG. This is the first time that a document has been put together which comprehensively describes the working of the Eureka search interface in the context of the contents of the HPB. It is hoped that the manual will offer a great deal of assistance to the users of the HPB in your reading rooms, as well as your cataloguing staff. The manual will be updated regularly, and comments from members will be included as appropriate.

Printed version

Two bound copies of the manual will be sent to all members. Further copies of the manual can be ordered from the Executive Manager at a cost of £8.50 per copy, to cover printing costs and postage.

Web version

The manual is also available on CERL's website: <http://www.cerl.org/manual/manonline.htm>. There will be a direct link from the HPB on Eureka on the Web to this on-line manual.

Organisational news

Executive Committee and ATG

The ATG and EC met on 9 and 10 March in Edinburgh. The most important issues on the agenda were UNIMARC output (see below) and the development of an HPB Thesaurus file.

The Thesaurus file will function as a tool for assisted searching, thus rendering the entering of multiple search terms of the various alternative forms of a name unnecessary. The meeting expressed particular thanks to Werner Schwartz and the DataConversionGroup in Göttingen who have been responsible for much of the initial development of the thesaurus file. A proto-type, containing variant forms of place names is available in a test environment.

Ann Matheson

RLG will examine the possibilities for linking the Thesaurus file to HPB. The alternative forms of names will be taken from the Thesaurus file and will all be used as search terms in the HPB.

Finance Committee

The Finance Committee (M. Smethurst (Chair) Prof. E. Mittler (Treasurer), L. Hellinga, A. Matheson and M. Crump) met on 17 May to draft a budget for the year 2000-2001.

In this financial year the subscription rate for the next funding period of three years (October 2000 until September 2003.) will have to be set. The Company Secretary, Dr Lotte Hellinga, will send you more information on this issue shortly.

New Chair

Mike Smethurst will step down as Chair of the Consortium at the Full Members' meeting in November (Padua – 10 November, preceded by a half-day Seminar on 9 November, concentrating on activities in Italy).

Mike Smethurst, Tony Curwen, Werner Schwartz

A subcommittee of the Executive Committee has drawn up a list of criteria for the new Chair. In June/July this list of criteria will be distributed to all CERL members, and you will be invited to nominate suitable candidates for the election of the new Chair.

IT Officer

At the Full Members' meeting in Brussels (November 1999) the meeting agreed that CERL would seek to recruit an IT-officer to assist in the formulation of a database development strategy for its Hand Press Book database. The IT officer will also be responsible for the implementation of the strategy.

An interview panel consisting of M. Smethurst (Chair), L. Hellinga, A. Matheson (National Library of Scotland) and S. Ross (University of Glasgow) interviewed two candidates on 18 April. Neither of the candidates fitted the criteria for the post and the Board has not made an appointment. The Board is investigating whether it should re-advertise or find other methods of tapping into the expertise and experience required for the execution of the HPB development programme.

UNIMARC output

In March of this year all CERL members received a questionnaire, which aimed to establish whether CERL members require a download facility for UNIMARC formatted records, and whether the download facility proposed by RLG would meet their needs.

24 Members responded. 19 Members wish to download records from the HPB, and 10 wish to download records in UNIMARC format. Of those 10 institutions only five thought RLG's proposal was good value for money, and that the proposal more or less met their needs (though 2 would like extra interfaces to download from and one would like on-the-fly conversion). On the basis of these results the Executive Committee decided not to invest \$61,000 as proposed in RLG's downloading system, but to investigate further options.

The Executive Manager is now exploring a promising alternative with a company based in Britain. If accepted, the issue may be resolved and function in a few months' time.

File procedures, UNIMARC Cataloguing and CERL defined fields

On the CERL website a number of pages contain detailed information on procedures for loading information to the Hand Press Book database, abbreviated as FILPROC, as well as recommendations for UNIMARC cataloguing, including fields specifically used and defined by CERL, abbreviated as UNICAT. In the section CERL '9' Fields you will find a description of each of the CERL defined fields. This information is particularly relevant for those institutions interested in submitting records to CERL for inclusion on the HPB database. Please consult <http://www.cerl.org/unadintr.htm> for:

CERL File Procedures (FILPROC)

- The HPB database: date range and types of material
- File submitting, vetting, conversion etc.
- Maximum length of records, fields and subfields
- RLG dataloads
- Non-sorting characters and initial articles

UNIMARC and Cataloguing Rules (UNICAT)

- UNIMARC general
- UNIMARC: '9' fields; use by CERL and member libraries
- Countries and country codes
- Record identifiers, and CERL institution and file codes
- Fill characters, blanks and standard codes
- Fixed-length coded data subfields
- Authority file record numbers and cross references
- The UNIMARC record label

CERL '9' Fields

- CERL field 690 - Personal name used as subject - Alternative form
- CERL field 691 - Corporate body name used as subject - Alternative form
- CERL field 692 - Family name used as subject - Alternative form
- CERL field 790 - Personal name - Alternative form
- CERL field 791 - Corporate name - Alternative form
- CERL field 792 - Family name - Alternative form
- CERL field 899 - Location

Use of the databases offered by CERL

Use of all databases has increased significantly in the first six months of the financial year compared to those last year, which is a very encouraging development.

September 1998 – March 1999 September 1999 – March 2000

The blue column shows use in the first six months of the financial year 1998-1999 (September-March), the pink column shows the number of searches for the same period in 1999-2000. The last column shows the number of records that were downloaded from the HPB. The slight decrease in the number of records downloaded can be explained by an increase in records downloaded through Z39.50. The overall growth in use of the databases is obvious.